

The Influence of Transformational Leadership of Principals of Wenzhou Private Middle Schools on Teachers' Job Satisfaction -- Psychological Capital as Mediating Variable

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Abstract

Transformational leadership is the process by which leaders construct a vision for the organization and, through communication and motivation, meet the high-level needs of employees, gain their acceptance of the organization's goals, change the organization's original values, interpersonal relationships, and organizational culture, and pursue superior organizational benefits. The teacher job satisfaction refers to the general attitude of teachers towards their profession and working conditions. The job satisfaction of private secondary school teachers in Wenzhou is low, especially in terms of compensation, benefits and promotion opportunities, and they are basically dissatisfied with the rules and regulations and professional identity. The purpose of this study is to study the relationship among principals' transformational leadership, teachers' psychological capital and teachers job satisfaction, and to construct a theoretical model of the influence of principals' transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction with teachers' psychological capital as the intermediary variable, thus putting forward feasible countermeasures for private secondary schools in Wenzhou to improve teachers job satisfaction. The study uses a questionnaire survey to collect first-hand data from 882 private secondary school teachers in Wenzhou. The collected data is analyzed using SPSS and AMOS software to obtain the research result. According to the findings of the study, private secondary schools in Wenzhou should be based on the mechanism of the principal's transformational leadership and teachers' job satisfaction, and the principals of private secondary schools should be given strategic suggestions to improve teachers' job satisfaction in four aspects: adjusting the principal's leadership style, giving teachers individualized consideration, emphasizing school inspirational motivation, and developing teachers' psychological capital to help build their teaching force.

Keywords: *Transformational leadership, Teacher job satisfaction, Psychological capital.*

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Introduction

In Wenzhou, private schools, as an important part of basic education, play an important role for the education of Wenzhou City. In many private secondary schools in Wenzhou, the principal's leadership and teachers job satisfaction are increasingly becoming the key factors affecting school management. In February 2019, the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China and the State Council promulgated the programmatic document on education, "China's Education Modernization 2035", which makes overall strategic arrangements for China's educational reform and development. In order to adapt to the new programmatic requirements, schools must transform themselves to meet the needs of modernization (Zhao, & Xi, 2018). Transformational leadership, by considering the needs of each follower, encourage followers to seek new ways to deal with the challenge, and become more involved in their work (Yang & Gao, 2022). The leadership behavior led to higher commitment of followers, especially the emotional attachment to the organization. An empirical study shows that the principal's transformational leadership practice significantly affects teachers job satisfaction; Transformational leadership is a leadership theory proposed based on the western cultural context. It is a situational variable, and its mechanism may be affected by individual differences of employees. A meta-analysis pointed out that the effectiveness of transformational leadership in different situations will change considerably. The principal's transformational leadership can promote the transformation from individual capital to organizational capital, promote the improvement of teachers' self-efficacy, students' academic achievement, and increase teachers' and students' sense of identity with the school organization. Motivating private secondary school teachers and enhancing their psychological capital and job satisfaction have become imperative to improve the performance of private secondary schools. And the principal's leadership style and teacher's job satisfaction are closely related to the level of teachers' psychological capital. Teachers job satisfaction is closely related to teachers' work enthusiasm and physical and mental health, has an important influence on students' education and growth, and is an important indicator of school management performance. In the development process of building a high-quality professional teaching team, the attention to teachers' work satisfaction is an extremely important part. It determines teachers' work attitude and behavior, and is directly linked to teaching quality, which is the key to running education well in private secondary schools. The construction of the teacher team lays special emphasis on the function of the principal, who should care passionately about the teachers and escort the improvement of their job satisfaction. The author takes teachers in Wenzhou private secondary school as the research object, discusses the relationship between the secondary school principals' transformational leadership, teachers' psychological capital and teachers job satisfaction, reveals the importance of the secondary school principals' transformational leadership, which affects teachers job satisfaction through psychological capital. The research of this paper will contribute to the reform and innovation of Wenzhou private education, and make the teachers of Wenzhou private education a model of China's private education (Zhao & Xi, 2018).

Problem Statement

Teacher job satisfaction is a teacher's cognitive evaluation and emotional response to all aspects of his work, reflecting the teacher's work attitude, can affect the enthusiasm and initiative of teachers' work, affect the quality of teachers' work, and then affect the quality of education (Yang & Gao, 2022). The concept of job satisfaction was formally proposed by Hoppock (1935) in his doctoral paper "Job Satisfaction." Since Hoppock, job satisfaction has become the most frequently studied variable in the field of organizational behavior. Many researchers apply job satisfaction to enterprises, public sector, education and other fields. It can be said that teacher job satisfaction is not only an important parameter to measure the quality of teachers' work, but also closely related to teachers' professional commitment, work

initiative, psychological capital, teaching efficacy, and so on. Conley and Levinson (1993) proposed that the success of an organization depends on the energy invested by the supreme leader and his insight into organizational management. Therefore, as the "man at the wheel" of a school, the principal's leadership plays an important role in stimulating teachers' attitudes and behaviors. Xu and Zhang (2011) suggested that teachers' job satisfaction is closely related to their principal's leadership. Nowadays, the practical tasks such as performance appraisal, professional title evaluation and whether the promotion rate is improved make teachers' work pressure accumulate constantly. Research has shown that school management measures such as salaries to achieve benefit exchange to meet teachers' needs can play an important role through economic leverage in the early stage of education reform, but it is now difficult to get good results by relying solely on external rewards and punishments to relieve teachers' stress and change their work attitudes (Yang & Gao, 2022; Zhao, & Xi, 2018). Therefore, in order to improve teachers' job satisfaction, it is necessary to break through the traditional leadership style for teachers, which puts forward the requirements for the transformation of the principal's leadership style. Compared with corporate employees, teachers have more autonomy in teaching and administrative affairs, so in a school environment with a loose structure and a tight culture, simply using top-down contract exchanges cannot change teachers' attitudes more deeply and get their heartfelt recognition. Only when principals transform their leadership style into using value addition to build a mutually negotiated vision with teachers, evoking their identification with organizational goals, and thereby generating intrinsic commitment, can teachers' latent competence and sincere satisfaction be evoked from the perspective of values, and this is just when transformational leadership can come into play. With the continuous development of leadership theories, humanistic care-oriented leadership has attracted more and more attention from scholars. Among them, transformational leadership theory, which belongs to a new leadership paradigm, is characterized by leading subordinates by establishing common value vision and humanistic development strategies (Einar, & Sidsel, 2011). From this point of view, the study on the effectiveness of transformational leadership is in line with the current reality of education development, especially for private secondary school teachers with serious professional pressure and burnout under the background of education reform, its effectiveness is more worthy of in-depth discussion and attention (Yang & Gao, 2022). The non-instrumental characteristics of transformational leadership are clearly more in line with the current school development than traditional contractual leadership, and although its positive effect on job satisfaction has been confirmed by many studies in the corporate arena (Huang, Wu, & Zhu, 2012), the mechanism of the effect between the two still needs to be further examined in depth. If only to verify the relationship between the two, the exploration is still at the shallow stage of exploring the results of the relationship. In recent years, related research has likened the mechanism of transformational leadership and outcome variables to a "black box", and is working to study the possible mediating variables on the path of influence. Unraveling the mystery of the "black box" has become a frontier topic of related research. Ji, Feng, & Zhao (2022) proposed to enhance teachers' job satisfaction by strengthening the development of principals' transformational leadership style, playing an active role in principals' transformational leadership, paying attention to teachers' emotional needs, parallelizing appropriate empowerment and personalization, establishing a common vision, and stimulating teachers' motivation for curriculum reform. Yang and Gao (2022) proposed that teachers' psychological capital is closely related to their work investment. Secondary school principals should pay attention to the development of teachers' psychological capital, pay attention to the dynamic changes of teachers' psychological capital and work investment in the management process, and guide teachers to maintain a high-spirited psychological state and full working state. This study will explore the role of teachers' psychological capital in the relationship between

principals' leadership and their job satisfaction from the perspective of teachers' psychological energy and state, which has profound significance both for the exploration and disclosure of the theoretical "black box" and for the development of principals' actual leadership. To sum up, investigating the impact of principals' transformational leadership on teachers' satisfaction in their positions through actual surveys and exploring the mechanism of the two is of profound significance in stimulating positive energy in teachers' work, changing their work attitudes, and transforming principals' leadership style, thus promoting school operation to a more humanistic pattern and higher value orientation. Based on the background of The Times, this study will take the leadership style with the characteristics of value addition and humanistic development as the starting point, and mainly explore the impact of principal's transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction. By introducing psychological capital as a mediating variable, this paper is committed to further investigating the influencing mechanism among variables and trying to dig deeper into the process of principal transformational leadership's effect on teachers' attitude.

Research Questions

Based on the problem statement, the specific issues addressed in this study are as follows:

1. What is the overall status quo of secondary school principals' transformational leadership, teachers' job satisfaction and their psychological capital?
2. What are the characteristics of the principal's transformational leadership, the teacher job satisfaction and their psychological capital in the teacher demographic variables?
3. Does the secondary school principal's transformational leadership have a significant positive impact on teacher job satisfaction? What are the differences in the impact of each sub-dimension?
4. Does teacher's psychological capital play a mediating role in the impact of secondary school principals' transformational leadership on teacher job satisfaction?

Literature review

Transformational Leadership of Principals

In order to cope with the intelligent age, school organizations need to transform themselves to realize the futurization, modernity and creativity of their students. Traditional leadership has been unable to meet this need. Just as Ted Dintersmith (2018) said in the "What school could be", "If education can be based on the understanding of the real world, it can help students explore various life development paths during their study." Leadership theory has evolved with the development of The Times. The theoretical assumptions formed in each period are different and have their own characteristics. The first to appear is the trait theory, which advocates looking for the unique characteristics of successful people who become leaders compared to their subordinates, emphasizing that Heroes decide the course of history. Then behavior theory came out, which began to focus on summarizing the actual explicit dynamic behavior of successful leaders, rather than personality traits. The research mainly examined what successful leaders do, how to do it in actual management, and what is unique (Jiang, & Lan, 2012). Both of these early leadership theories have the shortcoming of "generalizing from one side to the other". Due to differences in leadership situations and different subordinates, there is no universal set of traits or behaviors that are universal to successful leaders. As a result, the contingency theory of leadership is formed, which mainly combines situational factors with other factors in the leadership process to carry out research, and advocates adopting leadership styles that are consistent with employees, time, and environments (Peter G. Northouse, Wu, et al. Trans, 2002). It can be seen from this that the leadership theories formed in each period focus on discussing leadership issues from different perspectives, and the evolution of viewpoints at each stage is a process of perfecting the overall leadership

theory. In the 1980s, a new paradigm-oriented leadership theory, which combines the culmination of the above three traditional leadership theories, emerged. It is completely different from the previous way of thinking that leaders are managers. Instead, more attention should be paid to the higher needs and self-actualization of subordinates, thereby stimulating organizational morale through intrinsic commitment. The emergence of new paradigm leadership theory provides new ideas for the development of related research. Transformational leadership theory belongs to the new paradigm of leadership theory, and it has received extensive attention from scholars for its humanistic concern and value-added themes. It was first proposed by Burns (1978) and systematically elaborated by Bass (1985), who believed that transformational leadership refers to a leadership style that provides employees with an approved vision and higher-level needs in order to promote their intrinsic commitment and make them naturally willing to follow and obey the leader (Bass,1995). After the theory was proposed, it was widely used in the related research of enterprise management. Leithwood et al. (1990) first confirmed the effectiveness of transformational leadership in solving the challenges faced by principals under the background of the school reform wave initiated by the Western "School Restructuring Movement", and improved the connotation of transformational leadership based on educational management through continuous research: By establishing a common vision and organizational goals shared by teachers, and building a collaborative campus culture using humanistic care, teachers will be able to evoke internal recognition and stimulate their potential for learning and growth, and thus be more effective in the development of school change. Based on the theory of transformational leadership, Leithwood (1990) concluded that, compared with the traditional leadership style, the connotation of the principal's transformational leadership presents two most significant characteristics: First, the principal replaces the "manager" as a "leader", effectively distinguish "leader" from "manager", pay more attention to the development of teachers as human beings, and take people-oriented care as the main theme of leadership. Principals under traditional leadership tend to play the role of school administrators, focusing on work procedures and resource allocation, emphasizing the regular operation of the school. The principal of transformational leadership plays the role of the school leader, emphasizes humanistic care for each subordinate, advocates that the principal provide teachers with personalized attention, trust, appreciation, and other forms of spiritual rewards, truly achieves "people-oriented", makes teachers feel the importance and appreciation from the principal, and shapes the cooperative organizational atmosphere among teachers (Yu, Leithwood, & Jantzi,2002), thus mobilizing their thinking activity and stimulating their potential professional ability. Second, the principal's transformational leadership also emphasizes the guidance of teachers' values and awakens their higher-level psychological needs, which go beyond the previous expectations of work limited to the level of exchange of benefits. Rather, it is about building a shared vision that outlines a simple and understandable blueprint for the school's organizational development and speaks to teachers about a future that they can recognize as credible and attractive. At the same time, sharing common moral values with members of the organization, promoting individual teachers to have a higher level of moral responsibility, helping them to establish a link between the school's organizational goals and their own self-realization goals, and in the current era of rapid school change, it is more conducive to harvesting teachers' superior work action and performance. After Bass (1999) formally proposed the connotation of transformational leadership, after a period of development, he finally divided it into four dimensions: inspirational motivation, individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, and leadership charisma, and then formed the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ). MLQ is a mature and classic transformational leadership measurement tool, which has been proven to have good reliability and validity through research and reference by many scholars (Feng, 2016).

When Chinese scholars introduced the theory of transformational leadership to China, considering the particularity of the Chinese situation, and based on Western theories, they carried out localized thinking on its structure and measurement. The most influential viewpoint comes from Li and Shi. They believe that the special dimension of "moral character" is indispensable in local transformational leadership. Under the influence of long-term Confucianism, high collectivism and power distance, the members of Chinese organizations will "be convinced" based on the leader's personal moral character, thus replacing the intelligence stimulation dimension in Bass's theory and forming the four dimensions of Chinese transformational leadership: individualized consideration, leadership charisma, inspirational motivation, and moral modeling. Then the Transformational Leadership Questionnaire (TLQ) was designed accordingly, which has been applied in a large number of empirical studies and verified its good reliability and validity (Li, & Shi, 2005).

Focusing on the current measurement of the principal's transformational leadership, almost all of them directly apply the dimension division and measurement tools of Bass or Li. After comparing the two in detail, it is found that the utilization rate of Bass' viewpoint is relatively low. For example, Li et al. (2006) used the MLQ questionnaire to investigate the leadership behavior of the principals of ordinary high schools in Shandong. On the contrary, Li's view has the highest proportion of references in relevant studies. For example, Yu and Bai (2011), Cao (2007), and many other researchers have directly used the TLQ questionnaire to collect relevant data on the transformational leadership style levels. However, with the re-discussion of the characteristics of transformational leadership at home and abroad, some scholars have begun to raise appropriate doubts on the dimension division view of Li, which has the highest proportion of references. For example, Meng (2013) pointed out that the dimension of "intellectual stimulation" in Bass's four-dimensional structure is an important link to promote employees' divergent thinking and awaken their creativity. Innovation ability is exactly the ability that employees are most required to possess under the background of rapid changes and fierce competition in China, so it cannot be directly removed as Li's point of view. In addition, the "moral modeling" dimension advocates leading by example, its essence still comes from the leader's own personality charm, its connotation and the "leadership charisma" dimension inevitably overlap. In summary, this study considers using the TLQ questionnaire, which is based on the local context and more mature in China, as a basis, and taking into account its shortcomings as currently proposed by scholars, and organically combining it with the MLQ questionnaire in accordance with the educational context, to form the structural division of transformational leadership of principals and the corresponding measurement tools in this study.

Teacher Job Satisfaction

The structural composition of job satisfaction has two types of orientations: one considers it as a unidimensional structure that does not involve the satisfaction dimensions, echoing the comprehensive definition of the connotation, and asserts that it is a synpaper of comprehensive cognitive and affective feedback about the job. The other type advocates a multidimensional structure, echoing the dimensionality definition, and advocates the dimensional division of satisfaction. From this, the structure presents a multidimensional situation. Vroom's (1962) seven-dimensional theory (including work content, promotion, and other seven dimensions) and Smith et al.'s (1969) five-dimensional theory (including the five dimensions of boss, salary, and work itself, etc.) are more classic. As far as teacher job satisfaction is concerned, this study supports the dimensional definition of its connotation, so it thinks that its structure should be composed of multiple dimensions, but there is no unified standard for the current division. He (2007) divided teacher job satisfaction into seven dimensions, such as school leadership and

work pressure, etc. Mu et al. (2016) divided it into five dimensions: interpersonal relationship, pay-return, and school leadership, etc. Li et al. (2017) divided into seven dimensions: salary, training opportunities, school hardware and principal leadership, etc. On the whole, although the division methods are different, two common points can be summarized: (i) most studies divided into five or seven sub-dimensions; (ii) dimensions such as school leadership, salary and benefits, and interpersonal relationships received common attention and recognition from the vast majority of scholars.

Teachers' Psychological Capital

Luthans (2007), after testing several human positive psychological elements, selected those that best met the criteria of positive organizational behavior and combined them with positive psychology to form the four dimensions of psychological capital, including resilience, hope, self-efficacy, and optimism. Based on this, he developed the Psychological Capital Questionnaire (PCQ-24). This "state-oriented" structural division is widely accepted, and most relevant studies have adopted this perspective. When Liu et al. (2016) investigated the psychological capital of rural primary and secondary school teachers, and Chen Yan (2017) studied the effect of teachers' psychological capital on their organizational citizenship behavior, they both used the four-dimensional structure of Luthans and PCQ-24 questionnaire. In addition to the direct application of the PCQ-24 questionnaire by domestic scholars for empirical research, some other scholars have made appropriate improvements to the questionnaire in the local context of China, among which the most widely cited is the Teacher Psychological Capital Questionnaire revised by Zhang and Wen (2010), which follows a four-dimensional division and is more frequently cited in the measurement of psychological capital of early childhood teachers, such as the studies of Ji (2014) and Liu (2016). With the introduction of psychological capital theory, psychological capital measurement tools developed according to the specific enterprise situation in China came into being. In contrast to the Western culture, where personal factors are dominant, in the local context, interpersonal support from the surrounding people also brings more positive psychological power to the people in the workplace. Ke Jianglin (2009) summarized the foreign four-dimensional structure as a task-type factor into one large dimension, set the indispensable interpersonal emotion-type factor in the local context as another large dimension, and then constructed a complete two-dimensional and hierarchical structure, and thus form a questionnaire. It is rare for this structure to be cited in the field of education, and Mao (2015) has used it in several studies on teachers' psychological capital. Taken together, Luthans' four-dimensional structure and PCQ-24 questionnaire are the most frequently cited in relevant research at home and abroad over the years. In addition, although more domestic scholars have also designed localized psychological capital measurement instruments for teachers in Chinese educational contexts, e.g., Wu and Liu et al. (2012) constructed a structure of localized psychological capital of primary and secondary school teachers based on the perspective of cultural differences between East and West, specifically containing transactional psychological capital (hope, optimism, and perseverance) and interpersonal psychological capital (self-effacement, gratitude, altruism, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy). Mao (2013) believes that there are 9 factors in the psychological capital of primary and secondary school teachers and can be divided into two dimensions: task-based psychological capital (self-efficacy, resilience, hope, optimism, aggressiveness,) and interpersonal emotional psychological capital (enthusiasm, humor, fairness and integrity, and love and gratitude). At the same time, the research only on secondary school teachers found that teachers' psychological capital is a multi-dimensional and multi-level structural system, which mainly includes seven factors: teaching efficacy, hope, optimism, tenacity, communication and cooperation, and responsibility and tolerance, the first four can be classified as individual psychological capital, and the latter three can be classified

as relational psychological capital. To sum up, although there are differences in the nomenclature of dimensions or factors, it is generally believed that the structure of teachers' psychological capital includes two aspects: on the one hand, it is the psychological capital related to teachers' completion of teaching tasks, teaching work and teaching affairs, mainly including four factors of self-efficacy, optimism, hope, and tenacity, which are basically consistent with the factors that researchers in the field of psychological capital have generally paid attention to and have been continuously verified; on the other hand, there are psychological capitals related to interpersonal relationships and human relations, such as humility, gratitude, enthusiasm, and tolerance. However, due to the differences in research perspectives and group characteristics, the elements that researchers focus on are not the same, which needs to be further explored. Therefore, this study uses Luthans' four-dimensional structure (self-efficacy, hope, optimism, and resilience) to form the structural framework of teachers' psychological capital, and adjusts the PCQ-24 questionnaire in combination with the actual research situation to measure variables.

Research Framework

Based on the research questions and literature review, the theoretical model of this study is proposed, trying to explore the influence of the principal's transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction, and introducing teachers' psychological capital as a mediating variable to further analyze the mechanism of action between variables by verifying its mediating effect. In addition, this study also focuses and subdivides principal transformational leadership again, trying to explore the differences in the impact of each dimension on teachers' job satisfaction. The specific theoretical model is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Theoretical Model of This Study

Hypotheses

H1: Transformational leadership of principals has a significant positive impact on teachers' job satisfaction.

H1a: Principal's inspirational motivation has a significant positive impact on teachers' job satisfaction.

H1b: Principal's moral modeling has a significant positive impact on teachers' job satisfaction.

H1e: Principals' intellectual stimulation has a significant positive impact on teachers' job satisfaction.

H1d: Principal's individualized consideration has a significant positive impact on teachers' job satisfaction.

H2: Principal's transformational leadership has a significant positive impact on teachers' psychological capital.

H2a: Principal's inspirational motivation has a significant positive impact on teachers' psychological capital.

H2b: Principal's moral modeling has a significant positive impact on teachers' psychological capital.

H2c: Principal's intellectual stimulation has a significant positive impact on teachers' psychological capital.

H2d: Principal's individualized consideration has a significant positive impact on teachers' psychological capital.

H3: Teachers' psychological capital has a significant positive impact on their job satisfaction.

H4: Teachers' psychological capital mediates the effect of principals' transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction.

Methodology

Research Design

In this paper, quantitative and qualitative research methods are used in coordination. First of all, the literature research method was used. Secondly, 1000 teachers from 20 private middle schools in Wenzhou City were selected as samples to conduct a questionnaire survey and collect data information. Finally, SPSS software is used to complete data analysis.

Profile of Respondents

1. The current level of the president's transformational leadership

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics Table of Principals' Transformational Leadership

	Number of samples	Mean	Mean Sorting	Standard deviation	SD Sorting
Inspirational Motivation	882	3.953	3	0.816	3
Moral Modeling	882	4.030	2	0.903	2
Intellectual Stimulation	882	4.059	1	0.807	4
Individualized Consideration	882	3.570	4	0.921	1
Principals' Transformational	882	3.903		0.736	

As shown in Table 1, the overall mean of teachers' perceptions of principals' transformational leadership is 3.903, with a medium-high level of development; the standard deviation is 0.736, indicating that there is little individual variation in different principals' manifestations of transformational leadership and different teachers' perceptions of it. Focusing on the sub-dimensions, the scores in descending order of mean are: intellectual stimulation (M=4.059, SD=0.807) > moral modeling (M=4.030, SD=0.903) > inspirational motivation (M=3.953, SD=0.816) > individualized consideration (M=3.570, SD=0.921).

2. The current level of teacher job satisfaction

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics Table of Teachers' Job Satisfaction

	Number of samples	Mean	Mean Sorting	Standard deviation	SD Sorting
Work itself	882	3.775	3	0.696	3
Work Environment	882	3.905	2	0.687	4

Salary and benefits	882	2.911	5	0.907	1
Interpersonal Relationship	882	3.988	1	0.680	5
Promotion Development	882	3.465	4	0.838	2
Teachers' Job Satisfaction	882	3.609		0.697	

From Table 2, it can be seen that the overall satisfaction of teachers in private secondary schools in Wenzhou is 3.609, which is a medium-high level, and its standard deviation is 0.697, indicating that the teachers of private secondary schools in this survey are generally satisfied with their work, and there is little difference in the evaluation perception among different teachers. In terms of teachers' satisfaction with various aspects of their positions, in descending order of mean, they are: interpersonal relationships (M=3.988, SD=0.680) > work environment (M=3.905, SD=0.687) > work itself (M=3.775, SD=0.696) > promotion and development (M=3.465, SD=0.838) > salary and benefits (M=2.911, SD=0.907).

3. The current level of teachers' psychological capital

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics Table of Teachers' Psychological Capital

	Number samples	of Mean	Mean Sorting	Standard deviation	SD Sorting
Self-efficacy	882	4.149	1	0.533	4
Hope	882	3.882	2	0.607	2
Resilience	882	3.848	4	0.587	3
Optimism	882	3.858	3	0.685	1
Teachers' Psychological Capital	882	3.934		0.593	

It can be seen from Table 3 that the average level of the psychological capital of Wenzhou private secondary school teachers is 3.934, which is a medium-high level, and its standard deviation is 0.593, indicating that teachers generally present a better positive mental state, and the level gap between individuals is not large. In terms of each sub-dimension, in descending order of means, they are: self-efficacy (M=4.149, SD=0.533) > hope (M=3.882, SD=0.607), optimism (M=3.858, SD=0.685) > resilience (M=3.848, SD=0.587).

Correlation Analysis

Table 4 Pearson Correlation Table of The Main Variables Studied

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1 Inspirational Motivation	1						
2 Moral Modeling	0.643**	1					
3 Intellectual Stimulation	0.719**	0.737**	1				
4 Individualized Consideration	0.641**	0.741**	0.711**	1			
5 Principals' Transformational	0.853**	0.878**	0.898**	0.889**	1		
6 Teachers' Job Satisfaction	0.484**	0.494**	0.531**	0.517**	0.577**	1	
7 Teachers' Psychological Capital	0.358**	0.357**	0.387**	0.397**	0.427**	0.589**	1

Note: ** p<0.01

(1) Correlation analysis of principals' transformational leadership and its various dimensions with teachers' job satisfaction.

The overall correlation coefficient between the two variables is 0.577, reaching a significant level ($p < 0.01$), indicating that there is a significantly and moderately positive correlation between them, so Hypopaper H1 is initially supported. The four dimensions of transformational leadership of principals are also significantly and moderately positively correlated with teachers' job satisfaction, in descending order of correlation: intellectual stimulation ($r = 0.531$, $p < 0.01$), individualized consideration ($r = 0.517$, $p < 0.01$), moral modeling ($r = 0.494$, $p < 0.01$), and inspirational motivation ($r = 0.484$, $p < 0.01$), thus Hypotheses H1a-H1d are initially supported.

(2) Correlation analysis of principal's transformational leadership and its dimensions with teachers' psychological capital.

The overall correlation coefficient between the two variables is 0.427, reaching a significant level ($p < 0.01$), indicating that the two are significantly and moderately positively correlated, so the hypopaper H2 is initially supported. And the four dimensions of the principal's transformational leadership and teachers' psychological capital are all significantly and lowly positively correlated, in descending order of correlation: individualized consideration ($r = 0.397$, $p < 0.01$), intellectual stimulation ($r = 0.387$, $p < 0.01$), inspirational motivation ($r = 0.358$, $p < 0.01$), and moral modeling ($r = 0.357$, $p < 0.01$), so Hypopaper H2a-H2d is initially supported.

(3) Correlation analysis of teachers' psychological capital and job satisfaction.

The correlation coefficient between the two variables is 0.589, reaching a significant level ($p < 0.01$), indicating that the two are significantly and moderately positively correlated, so the Hypopaper H3 is initially supported.

Regression Analysis

1. Influence of principals' transformational leadership dimensions on teachers' job satisfaction
Multiple regression analysis is conducted to examine the effects of the dimensions of principals' transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction, and the F-value of the model is 165.318 ($p < 0.001$), which reaches a significant level, and the R^2 value is 0.334, indicating that the model has a high degree of explanation of the original data and the model fitting is ideal, as detailed in Table 5.

Table 5 Parameters of Regression Model of Principal's Transformational Leadership Dimensions on Teachers' Job Satisfaction

R	R ²	△ R ²	Standard Error	F
0.578	0.334	0.332	0.473	165.318***

Note: *, $p < 0.05$; **, $p < 0.01$; ***, $p < 0.001$

As shown in Table 6, the tolerance of the four dimensions of principals' transformational leadership ranges from 0.332-0.440, all between 0-1. The VIF values range from 2.271-3.015, all less than 10, indicating that the co-linearity situation among the independent variables in this regression model is well within the tolerance level and can be accepted. The regression coefficients of β for inspirational motivation ($\beta = 0.136$, $p < 0.001$), moral modeling ($\beta = 0.093$,

p<0.05), intellectual stimulation ($\beta=0.219$, $p<0.001$), and individualized consideration ($\beta=0.206$, $p<0.001$) to teachers' job satisfaction are all greater than 0 and all reach significant levels, thus indicating that all four dimensions of principals' transformational leadership have a positive effect on teachers' job satisfaction, and the Hypopaper H1a-H1d is supported.

Table 6 Regression Analysis of Principals' Transformational Leadership Dimensions on Teachers' Job Satisfaction

	Unstandardized coefficient		Standardized coefficient		Significance	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Standard error β		t		Tolerance	VIF
Inspirational Motivation	0.096	0.024	0.136	4.002	0.000	0.440	2.271
Moral Modeling	0.059	0.024	0.093	2.458	0.014	0.355	2.821
Intellectual Stimulation	0.157	0.028	0.219	5.610	0.000	0.332	3.015
Individualized Consideration	0.129	0.023	0.206	5.631	0.000	0.378	2.642

2. Influence of principal's transformational leadership dimensions on teachers' psychological capital

Table 7 Parameters of Regression Model of Principal's Transformational Leadership Dimensions on Teacher's Psychological Capital

R	R ²	Δ R ²	Standard Error	F
0.430	0.185	0.183	0.457	74.816***

Note: *, $p<0.05$; **, $p<0.01$; ***, $p<0.001$

Multiple regression analysis is conducted to examine the effect of the principal's transformational leadership on teachers' psychological capital, and the F value of the model is 74.816 ($p<0.001$), which reaches a significant level, and the R² value was 0.185, indicating that the model has a high degree of explanation of the original data and the model fitting is ideal, as detailed in Table 7. The independent variables in this regression model are the same as the independent variables in the aforementioned regression analysis of teacher job satisfaction, and they are all four dimensions of the principal's transformational leadership. Therefore, it has been proved that the collinearity between the independent variables is completely within the tolerance, and it can be been accepted. According to Table 8, the regression coefficients of β for inspirational motivation ($\beta=0.102$, $p<0.01$), moral modeling ($\beta=0.075$, $p<0.05$), intellectual stimulation ($\beta=0.142$, $p<0.01$) and individualized consideration ($\beta=0.204$, $p<0.001$) to teachers' psychological capital are all greater than 0 and all reach significant levels, which indicates that the four dimensions of the principal's transformational leadership have a significant positive impact on teachers' psychological capital, and the Hypopaper H2a-H2d is supported.

Table 8 Regression Analysis of Principal's Transformational Leadership Dimensions on Teachers' Psychological Capital

	Unstandardized coefficient		Standardized coefficient		Significance	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Standard error β		t		Tolerance	VIF
Inspirational Motivation	0.063	0.023	0.102	2.731	0.006	0.440	2.271

Moral Modeling	0.047	0.023	0.075	2.049	0.026	0.355	2.821
Intellectual Stimulation	0.089	0.027	0.142	3.288	0.001	0.332	3.015
Individualized Consideration	0.112	0.022	0.204	5.043	0.000	0.378	2.642

Analysis of Mediating Effect

1. Direct effect of principal's transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction

First, establish the direct effect model (M1) of the principal's transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction, as shown in Figure 4-1. By analyzing the direct effect of principals' transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction without mediating variables, to tests the research hypopaper and provides a basis for the subsequent comparison with the indirect effect with mediating variables.

Figure 2 Direct Effect Model (M1) of Principal's Transformational Leadership on Teacher Job Satisfaction

From Table 9, the model fitting results are: $X^2/df=4.732$, less than 5; RMSEA value is 0.086, less than 0.1; the values of TLI, CFI, and IFI are 0.944, 0.959, and 0.959, respectively, which are all greater than 0.9, and the goodness of fit is ideal; therefore, the overall model fitting of M1 is good.

Table 9 Fit Index Table for Direct Effect Model of Principal's Transformational Table Leadership on Teachers' Job Satisfaction

Indices	Standard value	Model output values	Fitting judgment
X^2/df	1-5	4.732	Good fit
RMSEA	<0.10	0.086	Good fit
TLI	>0.90	0.944	Good fit
CFI	>0.90	0.959	Good fit
IFI	>0.90	0.959	Good fit

According to the above fit indices and the path of principals' transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction, the direct effect path passes the significance test at the level of 0.001 and its standardized path coefficient value is 0.701, which is greater than 0 (see Table 4-20 for details), thus indicating that principals' transformational leadership has a direct and significant positive impact on teachers' job satisfaction in general, and Hypopaper H1 is supported.

Table 10 Direct Effect Model Path of Principal's Transformational Leadership on Teachers' Job Satisfaction

Paths	Estimate			S.E.	P
	Non-standardized	Standardized	C.R		
Principals' Transformational Leadership → Teachers' Job Satisfaction (direct effect)	0.391	0.701	18.622	0.021	***

Note: *, p<0.05; **, p<0.01; ***, p<0.001

2. Examination of the mediating role of teachers' psychological capital between principals' transformational leadership and teachers' job satisfaction. Based on the previous analysis, on the basis of verifying that the principal's transformational leadership has a significant positive and direct effect on teachers' job satisfaction, according to the research hypo paper, teachers' psychological capital is introduced as a mediating variable into the model to construct a mediating effect model (M2), as shown in Figure 3. From Table 11, the model fitting results are: $X^2/df=3.482$, less than 5; RMSEA value is 0.097, less than 0.1; the values of TLI, CFI, and IFI are 0.903, 0.923, and 0.923, respectively, which are all greater than 0.9, and the goodness of fit is ideal; therefore, the overall model fitting of M2 is good.

Table 11 Fit Index Table of Mediation Model

Indices	Standard value	Model output values	Fitting judgment
X^2/df	1-5	3.482	Good fit
RMSEA	<0.10	0.097	Good fit
TLI	>0.90	0.903	Good fit
CFI	>0.90	0.923	Good fit
IFI	>0.90	0.923	Good fit

Figure 3 Mediation Effect Model (M2) of Teachers' Psychological Capital

It can be seen from Table 11 and Figure 3 that in the mediation effect model, firstly, the standardized path coefficient value of the principal's transformational leadership on teachers' psychological capital is 0.445, which is greater than 0 and is significant at the 0.001 level, indicating that the principal's transformational leadership overall has a significant positive impact on teachers' psychological capital, so H2 is supported. Secondly, the standardized path coefficient value of teachers' psychological capital on their job satisfaction is 0.498, which is greater than 0 and is significant at the 0.001 level, indicating that teachers' psychological

capital has a significant positive impact on their job satisfaction, so H3 is supported. Moreover, after adding the mediating variables of teachers' psychological capital, the standardized path coefficient value of the indirect effect of the principal's transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction is 0.466, which is greater than 0 and is significant at the 0.001 level, indicating that the principal's transformational leadership also has a significant positive indirect effect on teachers' job satisfaction. The three positive impacts indicated by the above paths are all significantly established, which is the basic premise of the mediating effect.

Table 12 Path Diagram of The Mediating Effect Model

Paths	Estimate		C.R	S.E.	P
	Non-standardized	Standardized			
Principals' Transformational Leadership→ Teachers' Psychological Capital	0.209	0.445	13.629	0.015	***
Teachers' Psychological Capital→ Teachers' Job Satisfaction	0.65	0.498	13.648	0.048	***
Principals' Transformational Leadership→ Teachers' Job Satisfaction (Indirect effect)	0.286	0.466	15.726	0.018	***

Note: *, p<0.05; **, p<0.01; ***, p<0.001

On this basis, the mediating effects of teachers' psychological capital are examined by comparing the changes in the standardized path coefficients of principals' transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction between the unmediated direct effects model above and the present mediating effects model, as shown in Table 13.

Table 13 Comparison Table of Direct Effect Model vs. Mediating Effect Model Path of Principal's Transformational Leadership on Teachers' Job Satisfaction

Paths	Direct effect model		Intermediary effect model	
	Standardized coefficient	path _p	Standardized coefficient	path _p
Principals' Transformational Leadership→ Teachers' Job Satisfaction	0.701	***	0.466	***

Note: *, p<0.05; **, p<0.01; ***, p<0.001

In the model with the mediating variable of teachers' psychological capital, the standardized path coefficient of the principal's transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction is 0.466, which is significantly lower than the 0.701 in the direct effect of the two. It is shown that when teachers' psychological capital is added as a mediating variable, it weakened the direct effect of principals' transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction, which plays a mediating role in it. However, since the path between the two in the mediating effect model still reaches a significant level (p<0.001), indicating that even with the presence of the mediating variable of teachers' psychological capital, principals' transformational leadership still has some significant effect on teachers' job satisfaction, it is determined that teachers' psychological capital plays a partially mediating role, thus H4 is partially verified initially.

Table 14 Bootstrap Analysis of The Mediating Effect Of Teachers' Psychological Capital

Type of effect	Paths	Effect Size	SE	95 % confidence interval		
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound	P
Intermediary Effect	Principals' Transformational Leadership→ Teachers' Psychological Capital→ Teachers' Job Satisfaction	0.222	0.022	0.180	0.268	***

Note: *, $p < 0.05$; **, $p < 0.01$; ***, $p < 0.001$

The bias-corrected percentile bootstrapping method is used to further test the mediating effect of teachers' psychological capital, and the results are shown in Table 14. The mediating effect size is 0.222, the path of principal transformational leadership indirectly affecting teachers' job satisfaction through teachers' psychological capital is significant ($p < 0.001$); and the lower bound of the effect value is 0.180 and the upper bound is 0.268 in the 95% confidence interval, the whole interval does not contain 0, which meets the criteria and indicates that the effect exists. This fully indicates that in the impact mechanism of the principal's transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction, the partial mediating role of teachers' psychological capital is significant, and H4 is been partially verified.

Conclusion

The Overall Status Quo of Wenzhou Secondary School Principals' Transformational Leadership, Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Teachers' Psychological Capital Are All at a Medium-High Level, and There Are Differences in each dimension as concluded as the following (Li et al. 2018; Ji et al. 2022): (1) Principals are good at intellectual stimulation, but neglect individualized consideration. (2) Teachers perceived a positive relationship with colleagues and have a negative attitude towards salary and benefits. (3) Teachers have a strong sense of self-efficacy in the face of challenges and relatively weak resilience in the face of adversity. The Principals' Transformational Leadership, Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Teachers' Psychological Capital Are All Affected by Teacher Demographic Variables. Principal's Transformational Leadership Has a Significant Positive Impact on Teachers' Job Satisfaction. (4) The transformational leadership of principals is conducive to the improvement of teachers' job satisfaction. (5) There are differences in the strength of influence of the principal's transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction. Teachers' Psychological Capital Plays a Partial Mediating Role in the Positive Effect of Principal's Transformational Leadership on Teachers' Job Satisfaction. (Li et al. 2018; Ji et al. 2022; Demir 2018)

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